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Tell Me Where You Live, and I Will Predict Your Exercise Levels: How Self-Regulatory Action Control, Objective and Perceived Physical Environment Jointly Explain Physical Activity Time

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Abstract

Objectives: This study investigated how self-regulation indicators (self-regulatory effort, awareness of standards, self-monitoring) and perceived physical environment (perceived physical environment at home, in the neighbourhood, and availability of health promotion programs) are connected to explain moderate-to-vigorous physical activity (MVPA) over time. Furthermore, we examined, whether these associations were moderated by an “objective” environmental indicator, comparing large city (with more PA facilities) to small towns and rural areas (with fewer PA facilities).

Methods: Participants ($N = 593$) provided data twice, spanning eight months between the measurements. MVPA time was assessed using ActiGraph GT3X-BT accelerometers. Two-group mediation models were tested with path analysis.

Results: The associations represented in the mediating model, encompassing perceived neighborhood environment → awareness of standards → MVPA were significant and positive in the city (with more PA facilities) but not in towns/rural areas (with fewer PA facilities). High perceived availability of health promotion programs in towns/rural areas (with fewer PA facilities) may result in a paradoxical effect of lower MVPA.

Conclusions: The observed associations suggest distinct patterns of associations in the two types of physical environment and the importance of compatibility between the “objective” and perceived physical environment.

Keywords: physical environment; self-regulation; physical activity; rural areas

The significance of physical activity (PA), and in particular moderate-to-vigorous physical activity (MVPA), is undeniable, with its contribution to muscular and cardio-respiratory fitness, bone health, and reduced risk of hypertension, stroke, diabetes, or cancer (World Health Organization [WHO], 2020), as well as prevention of depression or anxiety (Katzmarzyk et al., 2022). Almost 500 million new cases of preventable major noncommunicable diseases will occur globally by 2030 if levels of PA would remain unchanged (Santos et al., 2023). Nevertheless, at least 25% of the global adult population remains insufficiently active (WHO, 2020). It leaves scope for disentangling the mechanism behind the relationship between PA and its predictors and translating this knowledge into practice.

Several health behaviour change models (e.g., the health action process approach, HAPA; Schwarzer & Hamilton, 2020) suggest that self-regulatory variables are the most relevant and proximal predictors of behaviours, such as MVPA. Self-regulation can be defined in terms of action control. In contrast to prospective self-regulatory cognitions (such as self-efficacy), self-regulatory action control as an in-situ strategy happens while the behaviour change is ongoing and it is structured into three subfacets (e.g., Sniehotta et al., 2006): awareness of standards (being conscious about one's intentions), self-monitoring (monitoring the behaviour in accordance with the intentions), and self-regulatory effort (effort put into reducing the divide between one's intentions and behaviour). Regarding various self-regulatory theories (Inzlicht et al., 2021), action control is derived from cybernetic models (CITE Carver & Scheier, 2002), highlighting the role of the feedback loops: specifically comparing the current state to desired goals, and emphasizing discrepancies between the current and desired state. A three-factorial action control intervention that focused on awareness of standards, self-monitoring, and self-regulatory effort has been shown to influence accelerometer-assessed PA at a 1-month follow-up positively? (Berli et al., 2018).

Other behaviour change models, such as ecological models or social-cognitive theory, indicate the importance of the interplay between self-regulation and environment, although the role of the former is assumed to be more prominent (Bandura, 1996; Luszczynska & Schwarzer, 2020; Sallis et al., 2006; Salmon et al., 2020). The concept of the "environment" encompasses factors such as physical characteristics of the neighbourhood (e.g., cycling facilities or other PA infrastructure), physical

characteristics of the home environment (e.g., sports equipment at home), as well as the social-cultural environment, such as the availability of programs promoting healthy living in the community (Sallis et al., 2006). The physical environment may be either operationalised as perceptions of the physical structures at home and/or in the local neighbourhood or as an actual number of PA facilities (e.g., football pitches, basketball courts, the length of cycling paths, etc.) in the respective area (Sallis et al., 2006). The operationalisation of the “objective” environment varies between studies. For example, each of the 20 studies reviewed by Menardo et al. (2022) applied a different set of characteristics of the “objective” environment, including a combination of bike facilities, land use mix, sports facilities, pedestrian facilities, traffic safety, street connectivity, and retail floor to area ratio. Using such indicators that rely on open-source data is assumed a standard approach to measure the “objective” environment (e.g., cf. Boeing et al., 2022; Rhodes et al., 2018).

Another approach is based on distinguishing between different types of “objective” environment, e.g., rural, suburban, and urban environments. In recent decades, PA levels have declined in the rural areas in Europe faster than in the urban areas (Moreno-Llamas et al., 2021). Besides mere rural-urban differences, there may be substantial discrepancies within the urban environment itself, with critical characteristics referring to the total population within a respective urban area. For example, in Poland, a threshold of 150,000 inhabitants is considered to discriminate between a large city and a smaller town/city (Statistics Poland, 2022). Compared to larger cities, inhabitants of smaller towns may perceive more infrastructural constraints, report limited access to PA facilities in their community, and be less likely to engage in PA (Badland & Schofield, 2006).

Ecological models (Sallis et al., 2026) stipulate that perceptions of the environment and the “objective” physical environment are conceptually distinct variables operating at different levels, with the “objective” environment being the most distant predictor of PA. “Objective” indicators represent actual physical structures present in the community. In turn, perceptions of the environment are complex representations shaped by past experiences, emotional and social processes, values, and length of living in the specific community (Orstad et al., 2017).

It may be assumed that the perceived and the “objective” environment operate jointly even if they are weakly related. The “objective” environment may predict perceptions of the environment (the

mediator), which in turn explain PA (Rhodes et al., 2020). However, a meta-analysis of research accounting for joint effects of the “objective” and perceived environment suggested that environment perceptions do not mediate the association between the “objective” environment and PA (Menardo et al., 2022). Alternatively, as proposed by Rhodes et al. (2018), “objective” physical environment indicators might moderate the effects of self-regulatory variables on PA (Rhodes et al., 2018). The evidence for this hypothesis, is also mostly unsupportive. A systematic review suggested that the effects of interactions between “objective” environment indicators and selected self-regulatory variables (other than action control or its subfacets) were mostly non-significant when explaining the total time spent on MVPA or PA (Rhodes et al., 2018).

Perceptions of the environment, which are hypothesized to be more proximal to the behaviour than the “objective” physical environment (Orstad et al., 2017; Sallis et al., 2026), may be directly related to self-regulatory beliefs, with these associations potentially operating in a bidirectional manner. Perceiving the environment as PA-promoting may enhance self-regulatory beliefs (e.g., awareness of one’s standards), which may, in turn, predict more time spent on PA. This path finds support in social cognition models like social-cognitive theory and ecological models, such as the four domains of active living (Luszczynska & Schwarzer, 2020; Salmon et al., 2020; Sallis et al., 2006). A reciprocal relationship may also be possible, with perceptions of the environment operating as a mediator between self-regulation and PA. For example, in line with social-cognitive theory (Bandura, 1996), one’s ability to self-regulate may make individuals prone to perceive the environment in a certain way, which may pave the way for the corresponding PA engagement.

The direct effects of the “objective” and “perceived” environment on PA, as well as self-regulatory mediating processes between environment indicators and PA, were extensively investigated (for reviews, see Menardo et al., 2022; Orstad et al., 2017; Rhodes et al., 2018, Rhodes et al., 2020). Unfortunately, many studies to date have been cross-sectional (for reviews, see Rhodes et al., 2018, Rhodes et al., 2020). Furthermore, some aspects have been rarely tested and require further evidence. First, the order in which the perceived environment and self-regulation are connected remains unresolved: does the perceived environment mediate the self-regulation—PA association, or is it self-regulation that mediates the relationship between the perceived environment and PA? Second, a joint

interplay between all three MVPA predictors, that is, the “objective” environment, the perceived environment, and self-regulation, continues to be understudied. In line with Sallis et al. (2006), we assume that the indicators of the “objective” environment form the most distant layer of PA predictors, that is: they may act as moderators of the associations between the perceived environment, self-regulation, and MVPA time. Third, previous research focusing on indicators of the “objective” environment, either accounted for the density of different types of PA facilities, safety of traffic, and connectivity, or compared urban to rural environment. Research combining “objective” indicators of PA facilities and urban-town/rural indicators to better capture the complexity of the physical environment is missing. Finally, it is unclear, whether a high level of one set of environmental factors may compensate for a low level of other factors, e.g., a high level of the perceived environment characteristics may compensate for a low level of the “objective” one.

To the best of our knowledge, there is no research so far examining if associations between the perceived environment, self-regulation, and PA may be moderated by the “objective” physical environment, defined as presence of the facilities (e.g., cycling, sports, and other type of leisure-time PA) and the population size living in a respective city/town/rural area (Steinführer et al., 2016). The present study investigated how self-regulation indicators (self-regulatory effort, awareness of standards, self-monitoring) and the perceived physical environment (the perceived physical environment at home, the perceived physical environment in the neighbourhood, and an aspect of socio-cultural environment, that is - the perceived availability of health promotion programs) are connected in explaining MVPA time. The study aimed to fill the void in current research by checking for (a) a mediating role of the perceived environment (measured at Time 2 [T2]; eight months after Time 1 [T1]) in the self-regulation (T1)—MVPA (T2) relationship (Model 1) and (b) a mediating role of self-regulation in the perceived environment (T1)—MVPA (T2) relationship (Model 2). Furthermore, we investigated if these associations were moderated by an indicator of the “objective” environment. In our study, we applied a binary indicator of the “objective” environment, comparing the large city (with more PA facilities) to towns and rural areas (with fewer PA facilities).

Method

Participants

At T1 593 participants provided their data; 543 participants (dropout of 8.43%) took part in the follow-up (T2). The baseline sample comprised in in 65.1% of women, with age ranging between 11 and 86 years old ($M = 33.79$, $SD = 16.78$). However, only 6.9% of participants were aged > 65 years old, and 13.5% were adolescents aged 11-18 years old. Among 37.1% who reported a chronic disease, the most frequent condition was hypertension with or without comorbidities (23.6%). Regarding participants' education, 37.4% had a higher education degree; 47.3% completed high school or had a vocational diploma or reported some post-secondary (non-tertiary) education; 3% reported primary education only. Approximately one half (47.6%) perceived their economic status as similar to the economic status of an average family in the country, 47.2% described their economic situation as above the average; and 5.2% reported their economic status as lower than average.

The following inclusion criteria were applied: (1) self-reported sedentary lifestyle, defined as spending the majority of waking time in a sedentary position and failing to meet the WHO (2010, 2020) recommended PA levels, that is > 60 minutes/day of MVPA for adolescents and > 150 minutes/week of MVPA for adults; (2) age \geq 12 years old; 11-year-olds ($n = 2$) who were at the same education level as 12 year-olds (T1) were also enrolled to prevent any sense of exclusion among adolescents recruited from the same grade.

Procedures

The study reported secondary findings of the randomized controlled trial (registration no. #NCT04131270 ClinicalTrials.gov). The primary outcome was sedentary time, with MVPA representing a pre-registered secondary outcome. The findings for the primary outcome indicated that compared to an active control condition (education + experiential knowledge techniques), an intervention involving active breaks planning (combined with education and experiential knowledge techniques) resulted in a similar reduction of sedentary time (see Krzywicka et al., 2024).

This study used data collected at two time points (T1 and T2), spanning eight months between the measurements. Participants wore accelerometers for six days at each time point. Accelerometer-based and self-reported data were collected individually during face-to-face meetings with an experimenter. Thirty-three investigators (psychologists or MA in psychology students) took part in at least two training sessions before the study. Data were collected between January 2020 and March 2022 in 15 cities or towns and 15 rural locations in South-Western Poland. Potential participants were informed about the study's objectives and procedures. Following their acquaintance with the study materials, they underwent eligibility screening. Informed consent was collected; in the case of adolescents, consent from their legal guardians was obtained in addition to their own consent. Personal codes were used to secure anonymity. The study received approval from the Ethics Committee at the first author's institution. Participants did not receive financial compensation, so a small thank-you gift (valued at 10 EUR) was offered after each assessment.

Measures

Means and standard deviations for the measures are displayed in Supplemental Material, Table S1.

Moderate-to-Vigorous PA Time (T1, T2)

MVPA time was captured by an ActiGraph GT3X-BT hip-worn accelerometer. At each measurement point (T1, T2), participants were asked to wear the accelerometer for a six-day period. Data were included in the analysis only if the device had been worn for at least eight hours a day, for a minimum of three days at each time point (Prescott et al., 2020). The first day of instructed wear time was removed from the analysis. Data scoring methods were based on Freedson VM3 algorithm (Sasaki et al., 2011; in case of participants aged 16 years or older) or on Evenson Children 2008 algorithm (Evenson et al., 2008; in case of participants younger than 16 years old), and processed in the Actilife software (version 6.13.4). Non-wear time was evaluated using an epoch-based algorithm based on Choi et al. (2011). Univariate outliers ($z > |3.29|$) were winsorised to one unit lower/higher than the next closest value in the distribution. PA time was operationalised as a sum of MVPA hours for each wear time period (T1, T2); very vigorous physical activity time was included for the adult

sample but was not accounted for in children/adolescents. Wear time at T1 and T2 was controlled for as a covariate of MVPA at the respective time points.

Self-Regulation (T1, T2)

Self-regulatory effort, self-monitoring, and awareness of standards were assessed with a self-report based on Berli et al. (2014) and Keller et al. (2015). Self-regulatory effort was assessed by three items, e.g., ‘I make an effort to train as much as I planned,’ and ‘In the last seven days, I really tried to exercise regularly’ (Cronbach’s α of .70 at T1, .76 at T2). Self-monitoring was evaluated using three items, e.g., ‘In the last seven days, I constantly monitored if I exercise frequently enough,’ ‘In the last seven days I constantly thought about undertaking PA’ (Cronbach’s α of .72 at T1 and .70 at T2). Three items were utilized to measure awareness of standards, e.g., ‘I regularly remind myself of being physically active,’ ‘I know exactly what my exercise or physical training program is’ (Cronbach’s α of .72 at T1, and .80 at T2). The response scale for the items regarding the three self-regulation aspects ranged from 1 (*definitely not*) to 4 (*definitely yes*). Mean item responses were used.

Perceived Environment (T1, T2)

A self-report measure, adapted from Shimotsu et al. (2007), was applied to assess the perceived physical environment at home, the perceived physical environment in the neighbourhood, and the perceived availability of health promotion programs. The perceived environment at home was assessed by six items, e.g., ‘Is there a weight lifting machine in your home?’, ‘Is there a stationary bike in your home?’. The internal consistency was moderate with KR-20 coefficient values of .57 at T1 and .53 at T2. The perceived environment in the neighbourhood measure employed five items, e.g., ‘Is there a gym or an exercise room in your neighbourhood area?’, ‘Is there a treadmill in your neighbourhood area?’ (KR-20 coefficient values of .88 at T1, and .89 T2). The perceived availability of health promotion programs in the local community was measured using six items, e.g., ‘Are there any physical activity events and activities in your area?’, ‘Are there any nutrition classes in your area?’. The consistency coefficient values (KR-20) equalled .73 at T1, and .73 at T2. The responses for all three indicators of the perceived environment were provided on a binary scale (0 = *no*, 1 = *yes*). Mean item responses were used.

Objective Environment (T1)

Respondents were recruited in two types of locations: (1) participants who lived in the large city (> 150,000 inhabitants, 58.9% participants) with a large number of public facilities for PA (including cycling paths, football pitches, basketball or volleyball courts, open-air and free of charge gyms), available at the lowest administrative unit of territory in Poland (“gmina”); (2) smaller towns (< 150,000 inhabitants; 21.9% of participants) or rural areas (19.2% of participants) with a substantially lower number of public facilities for PA (including cycling paths, football pitches, basketball or volleyball courts, open-air and free of charge gyms) available at the lowest administrative unit of territory in Poland (“gmina”). For example, the length of the cycling-friendly paths per unit of territory was > 1400 km in the first location category and 80 km or less in the second category. In sum, the variable was treated as dichotomous with the large city with more PA facilities compared to towns/rural areas with fewer PA facilities. For details, see Supplemental Material.

Covariates

Additional covariates in the sensitivity analysis model encompassed intention to engage in PA (T1), experimental condition (1 = *PA planning intervention*, 0 = *the active control group*), and sociodemographic variables such as gender, age, education, and economic status. PA intention (T1) was assessed by two positions, based on Maher and Conroy (2015): ‘I intend to engage in at least 30 min of moderate physical activity tomorrow,’ and ‘I intend to engage in at least 15 min of vigorous aerobic activity tomorrow.’ Responses varied from 1 (*definitely not*) to 4 (*definitely yes*). Spearman’s ρ coefficient equalled .508, $p < .001$. Education was measured by one item (response scale: 1 = *primary*, 2 = *vocational*, 3 = *secondary school*, 4 = *post-secondary*, 5 = *bachelor degree*, 6 = *higher education*). Perceived economic status was assessed using one question (‘How would you describe your family in terms of their economic situation?’), with answers ranging from 1 (*much above the average family in Poland*) to 5 (*much below the average family in Poland*). Education and economic status data were collected among adults only.

Data Analyses

Path analysis (IBM AMOS, version 29) was used to test the two hypothesized moderated mediation models. The models included either the perceived environment indicators as the mediators (Moderated Mediation Model 1) or self-regulation indicators as the mediators (Moderated Mediation Model 2), with the “objective” environment (the large city with more PA facilities vs. towns/rural areas with fewer PA facilities) operating as the moderator. The two hypothesized 2-group models accounted for two measurement points (T1, T2). The independent variables were assessed at T1, whereas the mediators and the dependent variables were evaluated at T2. Dependent variables (MVPA) at T1 were controlled for. The models were adjusted for accelerometer wear time by adding wear time hours from the corresponding measurement point as covariates.

A cut-off point of $\geq .95$ implied good model-data fit for the comparative fit index (CFI; Byrne, 2016) and the normed fit index (NFI; Byrne, 2016). For the root mean square error of approximation (RMSEA), a cut-off point of $\leq .08$ was applied (Byrne, 2016). The simple indirect effects were calculated using the user-defined estimands function (Amos Development Corporation, 2021). Missing data were accounted for with full information maximum likelihood estimation procedures (Byrne, 2016).

Mardia's coefficient of multivariate normality implied moderate non-normality. In Model 1, ‘Self-regulation \rightarrow Perceived Environment \rightarrow MVPA’: 5.372 for the towns/rural areas group (with fewer PA facilities), and 9.351 for the large city group (with more PA facilities). In Model 2, ‘Perceived Environment \rightarrow Self-regulation’ \rightarrow MVPA’: 6.466 for the towns/rural areas group (with fewer PA facilities), and 7.384 for the large city group (with more PA facilities).

Analytic Strategy for the Moderated Mediation Models

The two models differed in the order the variables were connected, predicting MVPA (T2). The order was as follows: in Model 1, ‘Self-regulation (T1) \rightarrow Perceived Environment (T2) \rightarrow MVPA (T2)’ and in Model 2 ‘Perceived Environment (T1) \rightarrow Self-regulation (T2) \rightarrow MVPA (T2)’. Employing two separate models rather than a single one helped mitigating the bias arising from multicollinearity and achieving a more satisfactory power of analysis by reducing the number of

parameters within each model. Ideally, each mediator should be measured at a different time point to establish a temporal precedence (MacKinnon, 2008). As the present study used only two measurement points, we decided to include T2-mediator indicators. This choice was made assuming the bias related to assessing the independent variable and the mediator with common methods (self-report) may be more substantial than combining a retrospective self-report of the mediator at T2 with an “objective” assessment of MVPA for six days, following the assessment of the self-report.

Two-group models were calculated, testing the differences in patterns of associations in the large city with more PA facilities, compared to towns/rural areas with fewer PA facilities. The independent variables were assumed to covary, as were the residuals of all the mediators. The baseline level of MVPA was included as the predictor of MVPA at T2. Accelerometer wear time at T1 and T2 indicators were covariates of MVPA at T1 and T2.

For each model a sensitivity analysis was performed to evaluate the robustness of findings (Thabane et al., 2013), controlling for age, gender, experimental condition, and PA intention (T1). Additional analyses were conducted in the subsample of adults ($n = 516$), accounting for the same set of covariates as the main sensitivity analysis, as well as education and economic status, which were assessed among adults only.

Results

Preliminary Analyses

Attrition analyses revealed that completers and those who dropped out at T2 did not differ in gender, economic status, education, PA intention, T1 MVPA, the perceived physical environment at home (T1), or the perceived physical environment in the neighbourhood (T1). However, they differed in age, self-regulatory effort (T1), self-monitoring (T1), awareness of standards (T1), and in the perceived availability of health promotion programs (for details, see Supplemental Material). Bivariate correlations among the study variables are presented in Supplemental Material in Tables S2 and S3.

The next set of preliminary analyses tested how the three types of variables included in Moderated Mediation Models 1 and 2 changed over time. There was a significant reduction in minutes of MVPA between T1 and T2 measurements, $F(1, 592) = 4.32, p = .038, \eta^2 = .007$ (T1: $M = 404.08, SD = 196.03$, T2: $M = 389.88, SD = 196.04$), Cohen's $d = 0.07$. Regarding self-regulatory variables,

there was no significant change over time neither in self-regulatory effort, $F(1, 592) = 2.13, p = .144, \eta^2 = .004$, nor in awareness of standards, $F(1, 592) = 0.09, p = .765, \eta^2 < .001$. Self-monitoring significantly decreased from T1 to T2 measurement $F(1, 592) = 6.92, p = .009, \eta^2 = .012$ (T1: $M = 2.31, SD = 0.66$, T2: $M = 2.23, SD = 0.66$). Regarding the perceived environment, there was no significant change in the perceived physical environment at home, $F(1, 592) = 1.44, p = .230, \eta^2 = .002$, the perceived physical environment in the neighbourhood $F(1, 592) = 0.07, p = .789, \eta^2 < .001$, or the perceived availability of health promotion programs, $F(1, 592) = 3.12, p = .078, \eta^2 = .005$.

Large City with More PA Facilities vs. Towns/Rural Areas with Fewer PA Facilities

There were no differences in MVPA time (T1, T2) for residents of the large city with more PA facilities compared to inhabitants of towns/rural areas with fewer PA facilities.

Self-regulatory effort (T1) was lower in the large city with more PA facilities ($M = 2.40, SD = 0.64$) than in towns/rural areas with fewer PA facilities ($M = 2.55, SD = 0.62$), $t(591) = 2.89, p = .004$, Cohen's $d = 0.63$. There was a difference in self-monitoring (T1, T2) at T1 $t(591) = 3.07, p = .002$, Cohen's $d = 0.65$, and at T2 $t(591) = 2.14, p = .033$, Cohen's $d = 0.66$, with lower levels of self-monitoring occurring in the large city with more PA facilities (T1: $M = 2.25, SD = 0.65$; T2: $M = 2.19, SD = 0.64$) compared to towns/rural locations with fewer PA facilities (T1: $M = 2.41, SD = 0.67$; T2: $M = 2.31, SD = 0.69$). Self-regulatory effort (T2) and awareness of standards (T1, T2) did not significantly differ across location groups.

Perceived physical environment at home (T1) differed between the two locations at T1 $t(430.772) = 5.27, p < .001$, Cohen's $d = 0.21$, and T2 $t(591) = 3.17, p = .002$, Cohen's $d = 0.20$. Specifically, the sample from the large city (with more PA facilities) reported lower levels of this variable (T1: $M = 0.24, SD = .20$; $M = 0.26, SD = 0.18$) than inhabitants of towns/rural areas (with fewer PA facilities; T1: $M = 0.33, SD = 0.24$; T2: $M = 0.32, SD = 0.23$). No differences between locations were found for the perceived physical environment in the neighbourhood (T1, T2) or the perceived availability of health promotion programs (T1, T2).

Regarding sociodemographic variables, both location did not differ in gender or economic status. There was, however, an age difference between participants, $t(471.963) = 2.09, p = .037$, Cohen's $d = 0.48$. Participants from the large city (with more PA facilities) were younger ($M = 32.60$,

$SD = 16.12$) as opposed to participants from towns/rural areas (with fewer PA facilities; $M = 35.59$, $SD = 17.61$). Adults ($n = 516$) from two distinct locations reported different education status, $t(499) = -4.99$, $p < .001$, Cohen's $d = 0.94$. Those from the large city (with more PA facilities) were more likely to have higher education levels ($M = 3.05$, $SD = 0.94$) than the residents of towns/rural areas (with fewer PA facilities; $M = 2.62$, $SD = 0.95$). Education levels were coded as follows: 1 = *primary education*, 2 = *secondary education*, 3 = *post-secondary education and bachelor's degree*, 4 = *higher education*.

Findings for Mediation Model 1, 'Self-regulation → Perceived Physical Environment → MVPA', Moderated by Objective Physical Environment

The hypothesised two-group model, calculated for the large city with more PA facilities ($n = 357$) and for towns/rural areas with fewer PA facilities ($n = 236$) had an acceptable fit, with $\chi^2(40) = 67.057$, $p = .005$, $\chi^2/df = 1.676$, NFI = .962, CFI = .984, RMSEA = .034 (95% CI [.019, .048]). Figure 1 and Table 1 present the path coefficients for the associations between the independent variables (T1), mediators (T2), and dependent variables (T2). The values of correlation coefficients are displayed in Supplemental Material, Table S4.

No significant indirect effects were found. Few associations between self-regulation indicators (T1) and the perceived physical environment (T2; see Table 1 and Figure 1) only few significant associations between the independent or mediator variables and MVPA time at T2 were observed. Among people recruited in the large city (with more PA facilities), a high level of the perceived physical environment in the neighbourhood (T2) was associated with higher MVPA (T2). Among people recruited in towns/rural areas (with fewer PA facilities), a higher level of the perceived availability of health promotion programs (T2) was associated with less time spent on MVPA (T2). We found no direct effects of self-regulation variables (T1) on MVPA time assessed eight months later.

Sensitivity analyses are reported in Supplemental Material, Table S5. In the analysis controlling for gender, age, intention to be physically active (T1), and the effects of the experimental group assignment, direct associations between the perceived physical environment (T2) and MVPA (T2) observed in the large city (with more PA facilities) and in towns/rural areas (with fewer PA

facilities) remained significant. An overall pattern of direct effects similar to the one obtained in the main model was confirmed, except for awareness of standards (T1)—perceived availability of health promotion programs (T2) relationship being no longer significant in towns/rural areas (with fewer PA facilities). The analyses conducted among adults only, controlling for education and economic status, are reported in Supplemental Material, Table S6.

Findings for Mediation Model 2, ‘Perceived Physical Environment → Self-regulation → MVPA’, Moderated by Objective Physical Environment

The hypothesised two-group model for the large city with more PA facilities ($n = 357$) vs. towns/rural areas with fewer PA facilities ($n = 236$) had an acceptable fit, with $\chi^2(40) = 77.722$, $p < .001$, $\chi^2/df = 1.943$, NFI = .960, CFI = .979, RMSEA = .040 (95% CI [.026, .053]). Figure 2 and Table 2 present the path coefficients for the associations between the independent variables (T1), mediators (T2), and dependent variables (T2). The values of correlation coefficients are displayed in the Supplemental Material, Table S7.

The Moderated Mediation Model 2 showed one indirect effect, observed in the group from the large city with more PA facilities: A higher level of the perceived physical environment at home (T1) predicted higher awareness of standards (T2), which in turn predicted more time spent on MVPA (T2), $B = 8.577$, $SE = 6.204$, $p = .035$, 95% CI [0.385, 27.461]. Although there were several associations between self-regulation indicators (T1) and the indicators of the perceived physical environment (T2) obtained (see Figure 2 and Table 2), there was only one additional direct association between the independent/mediator variables and MVPA time (T2). The perceived physical environment in the neighbourhood (T1) predicted higher MVPA time (T2) in the group recruited in the large city (with more PA facilities).

The sensitivity analysis, controlling for gender, age, PA intention (T1), and the experimental condition yielded similar findings to the one obtained in the main analysis (Supplemental Material, Tables S8-S9). The direct association between the perceived physical environment in the neighbourhood (T1) and higher MVPA time (T2) in the group recruited in the large city (with more PA facilities) remained significant. However, the association between the perceived availability of

health promotion programs (T1) and self-monitoring (T2) became non-significant in the large city (with more PA facilities) group. Still, the indirect effect remained stable. In the analysis conducted among adults only, controlling for education and economic status, the indirect effect also remained significant. Details are reported in Supplemental Material, Tables S10-S11.

Discussion

This study contributes to the ongoing discussion on the interplay between the “objective” physical environment, the perceived physical environment, and self-regulation - and their role in explaining MVPA. The findings were obtained adopting a prospective study design, accelerometer-based assessment of MVPA, and a heterogeneous sample, encompassing adolescents, adults, and older adults. Several recent systematic reviews of the original studies yielded disappointing conclusions regarding the role of the “objective” physical environment, which rarely forms a significant mediation with the perceived environment and PA, and rarely moderates the associations between self-regulation and PA (Menardo et al., 2022; Rhodes et al., 2018, Rhodes et al., 2020). Our study suggested an alternative approach, assuming the “objective” environment may operate as a moderator of the perceived environment → self-regulation → MVPA mediation. Moreover, the findings point towards the importance of compatibility between at-home and out-of-home environment and synergies/compatibility between the perceived health promotion programs in the local environment and the “objective” PA environment facilities.

The two-group model path analysis indicated only one mediating effect linking a higher level of the perceived physical environment at home to a higher level of awareness of standards, which in turn was associated with more time spent on MVPA. The mediation was true only for people from the large city with more PA facilities. In particular, this finding indicates that “objectively” abundant PA facilities outdoors combined with the perception of having rich PA equipment at home, was associated with more frequent thinking about and/or higher consciousness of intention/plans to exercise. Furthermore, higher awareness of standards was related to more time spent on MVPA only among people who lived in the large city (with more PA facilities). It seems that a combination of the “objective” out-of-home and at-home perceived environment should occur simultaneously to explain this facet of self-regulation and MVPA. These findings provide partial support for the four ecological models (e.g., Sallis et al., 2006, Salmon et al., 2020). However, neither the ecological models (Sallis et al., 2006, Salmon et al., 2020), nor previous research (yielding negligible associations between the “objective” and perceived environment, self-regulation, and MVPA (for reviews see Menardo et al.,

2022; Rhodes et al., 2018, Rhodes et al., 2020), have adequately addressed the need to consider the co-occurrence of PA-facilitating environments, both outside and inside the home. Accounting for the perceived physical environment at home may be important, as it is likely that the participants are exposed to their home environment cues daily, which may trigger PA or PA habits (e.g., see Hagger, 2019).

The findings also indicated that the perceived environment in the neighbourhood (measured at T1 and T2) was consistently associated with more time spent on MVPA, but only among residents of the large city with more PA facilities, compared to residents of towns/rural areas with fewer PA facilities. Previous research encompassing both the “objective” and perceived environment in the neighbourhood has mostly brought into focus the independent effects of both (Orstad et al., 2017) or potential mediation effects (Rhodes et al., 2020). In contrast, our study indicated a moderating effect, suggesting a compatibility effect: the perceived environment in the neighbourhood contributed to MVPA only among people living in the large city, rich in objectively assessed PA facilities.

Previous research often used continuous indicators of the “objective” physical environment, focusing on a combination of walkability, bike facilities, land use mix, sport facilities, traffic safety, street connectivity, etc. However, it usually did not directly account for urban-rural differences (Moreno-Llamas et al., 2021; Pfladderer et al., 2021) or city-town differences (Badland & Schofield, 2006). Larger cities may have a larger diversity and density of publicly available PA facilities, compared to the areas with smaller population density. The latter locations will have a larger percentage of the population that cannot reach public facilities for their preferred sports (e.g., skateboarding parks, volleyball courts) via public transportation. Our study compared the large city (characterized by one of the highest number of PA facilities in the country and high density of public transportation routes) with towns and rural areas (of much lower density and diversity of both PA facilities per km² and less frequent public transportation connections). Importantly, there were no differences in economic status across these two types of location, neither at the individual (perceived economic status), nor the objective level. The town and rural locations incorporated administrative units of higher, similar and lower average taxable income per capita, compared to the city included in our study. Future research addressing the role of the “objective” physical environment may need to

consider indicators combining the rural/town-city dimension (or at least the rural-urban dimension) combined with other indicators of community-based PA infrastructure (e.g., density and diversity) and its accessibility by public transportation.

Our findings point out a lack of the direct positive associations between the perceived physical environmental variables and MVPA as well as a lack of significant associations between self-regulation indicators and MVPA among inhabitants of towns/rural areas (with fewer PA facilities). Additionally, there was a negative link between the perceived availability of health promotion programs and MVPA among respondents living in towns/rural areas (with fewer PA facilities). Participants recruited in towns/rural areas (with fewer PA facilities) may perceive a gap between the access to PA programs (e.g., PA education or events) and the actual infrastructure facilitating everyday PA engagement in their local community. They may also sense a lack of compatibility between what is said (in terms of PA promotion) and what is done (in terms of the infrastructure) in their community. Respondents might also experience frustration when events promoting cycling or walking are launched within their town, but the number/density of cycling paths and facilities to walk remains insufficiently low. It is possible that discrepancies between promoted and actual physical activity opportunities that evoke frustration might lead to lower MVPA engagement. The alternative pathway may refer to the actual content of health promotion events, which may combine PA with healthy eating promotion. If participants of such events come to realise that PA facilities in their community are limited, they may engage more in formulating and pursuing their dietary goals.

Across the tested models, the observed associations were weak. This may be due to a substantial portion of accelerometer-measured MVPA at T2 being explained by baseline MVPA and because the timespan between T1 and T2 was relatively long (eight months). Due to the weakness of the effects observed, replications in other samples and context are particularly relevant before any implications for practice may be drawn.

Our study has several limitations. The design accounted for two data collection points only, with the mediator assessed at the same time point as the outcome variable. This choice was made assuming that the bias related to assessing the independent variable and the mediator with common methods (self-report) would be larger than the retrospective self-report of the mediator followed by an

objective assessment of MVPA for seven days. Ideally, the three measurement points should be separated by similar time periods. We did not control for the mediator level at the baseline due to multicollinearity issues, however, controlling for the T1 assessment of each indicator of action control would be preferable. The issue of collinearity also prevented us from combining the two mediation models into one model, accounting for all potential mediating paths at once. The objective indicator of the physical environment was based on comparing one city with the location of several towns and rural areas (all in the same region of Poland). Further research comparing more regions and combining data from several cities is needed, as well as potential three levels of moderator (namely: cities, towns, and rural areas) should be taken into consideration. Although the two types of location analysed in the present study did not differ in terms of perceived economic status or objective economic index of taxable income per capita, future studies should carefully reflect on more complex control of economic factors coming into play. Obtaining comparable perceived economic status data and education in samples comprised of children or adolescents is difficult. Hence, our main sensitivity analysis did not control for these variables. Examining any indicator of perceived economic status among adolescents and controlling for it would maximize the robustness of findings. Moreover, the study focused on specific aspects of self-regulation, namely: self-regulatory effort, self-monitoring, and awareness of standards. Various self-regulation models exist, differing in the emphasis placed on the role of emotions, cognitive functioning, and conflict (Inzlicht et al., 2021). Our approach to self-regulation confines to action control, which belongs to the family of cybernetic models of self-control (Inzlicht et al., 2021). Future research addressing other approaches to self-regulation (e.g., resource models of self-control or dual processes models) is warranted.

In conclusion, our findings suggest further complexity of the roles of the “objective” and the perceived physical environment, operating together with self-regulation in predicting MVPA. First, a combination of PA-promoting at-home (perceived) and out-of-home (“objective”) environment may be associated with accelerometer-assessed MVPA time. Second, the findings support the mediating model of the perceived neighbourhood environment → self-regulatory facet of awareness of standards → MVPA among inhabitants of cities (with more PA facilities), but not for those who live in towns/rural areas (with fewer PA facilities). Third, the high perceived availability of health promotion

programs in towns/rural areas (with fewer PA facilities) may result in a paradoxical effect of lower MVPA.

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Table 1

Model 1. Direct Effects for the “Self-regulation → Perceived Environment → MVPA Time” 2-group Mediation Model for the Towns/Rural Areas (With Fewer PA Facilities) Group (n = 236) and for the Large City (With More PA Facilities) Group (n = 357)

Variables and hypothesized associations	Towns/rural areas		Large city	
	β	p	β	p
Self-regulatory effort (T1) → Physical environment home (T2)	.025	.786	.304	<.001
Self-regulatory effort (T1) → Physical environment neighbourhood (T2)	.043	.670	.014	.868
Self-regulatory effort (T1) → Health promotion programs (T2)	-.112	.248	.103	.220
Self-regulatory effort (T1) → MVPA (T2)	-.104	.186	-.047	.422
Self-monitoring (T1) → Physical environment home (T2)	.120	.197	-.092	.262
Self-monitoring (T1) → Physical environment neighbourhood (T2)	-.044	.646	.033	.718
Self-monitoring (T1) → Health promotion programs (T2)	.188	.041	.164	.078
Self-monitoring (T1) → MVPA (T2)	.080	.302	.005	.960
Awareness of standards (T1) → Physical environment home (T2)	.107	.263	.051	.457
Awareness of standards (T1) → Physical environment neighbourhood (T2)	.174	.106	.101	.217
Awareness of standards (T1) → Health promotion programs (T2)	.188	.009	-.083	.354
Awareness of standards (T1) → MVPA (T2)	.083	.348	.049	.446
Physical environment home (T2) → MVPA (T2)	.026	.577	-.037	.347
Physical environment neighbourhood (T2) → MVPA (T2)	-.022	.677	.105	.023
Health promotion programs (T2) → MVPA (T2)	-.103	.037	-.031	.493
MVPA (T1) → MVPA (T2)	.630	<.001	.610	<.001

Note. T1 = Time 1, the baseline; T2 = Time 2, 8 months after T1; Significant coefficients are marked in bold; Model Fit: $\chi^2(40) = 67.057$, $p = .005$, $\chi^2/df = 1.676$, NFI = .962, CFI = .984, RMSEA = .034 (95% CI [.019, .048]). An additional covariate is Accelerometer wear time (T1, T2). MVPA = a sum of moderate-to-vigorous physical activity hours for each wear time period (T1, T2); very vigorous physical activity time was included for the adult sample, but was not accounted for in children.

Figure 1

Model 1. Direct Effects for the “Self-regulation → Perceived Environment → MVPA Time” 2-group Mediation Model for the Towns/Rural Areas (With Fewer PA Facilities) Group ($n = 236$) and for the Large City (With More PA Facilities) Group ($n = 357$)

Note. T1 = Time 1, the baseline; T2 = Time 2, 8 months after T1; * $p < .05$, ** $p < .01$, *** $p < .001$. Solid black arrows represent significant paths. Dashed grey arrows represent non-significant paths.

Table 2

Model 2. Direct Effects for the “Perceived Environment → Self-regulation → MVPA Time” 2-group Mediation Model for the Towns/Rural Areas (with Fewer PA Facilities) Group (n = 236) and for the Large City (with More PA Facilities) Group (n = 357)

Variables and hypothesized associations	Towns/rural areas		Large city	
	β	p	β	p
Physical environment home (T1) → Self-regulatory effort (T2)	.201	.003	.262	<.001
Physical environment home (T1) → Self-monitoring (T2)	.110	.098	.241	<.001
Physical environment home (T1) → Awareness of standards (T2)	.217	.001	.188	.001
Physical environment home (T1) → MVPA (T2)	.062	.248	-.038	.352
Physical environment neighbourhood (T1) → Self-regulatory effort (T2)	.076	.279	.071	.163
Physical environment neighbourhood (T1) → Self-monitoring (T2)	.059	.417	-.038	.482
Physical environment neighbourhood (T1) → Awareness of standards (T2)	.148	.031	.113	.039
Physical environment neighbourhood (T1) → MVPA (T2)	-.052	.304	.122	.005
Health promotion programs (T1) → Self-regulatory effort (T2)	-.021	.768	.015	.811
Health promotion programs (T1) → Self-monitoring (T2)	.003	.958	.122	.026
Health promotion programs (T1) → Awareness of standards (T2)	-.083	.224	.076	.179
Health promotion programs (T1) → MVPA (T2)	-.077	.180	-.035	.423
Self-regulatory effort (T2) → MVPA (T2)	.128	.138	-.118	.100
Self-monitoring (T2) → MVPA (T2)	.015	.922	.059	.359
Awareness of standards (T2) → MVPA (T2)	-.091	.335	.157	.039
MVPA (T1) → MVPA (T2)	.627	<.001	.598	<.001

Note. T1 = Time 1, the baseline; T2 = Time 2, 8 months after T1; Significant coefficients are marked in bold; Model Fit: $\chi^2(40) = 77.722$, $p < .001$, $\chi^2/df = 1.943$, NFI = .960, CFI = .979, RMSEA = .040 (95% CI [.026, .053]). An additional covariate is Accelerometer wear time (T1, T2). MVPA = a sum of moderate-to-vigorous physical activity hours for each wear time period (T1, T2); very vigorous physical activity time was included for the adult sample, but was not accounted for in children.

Figure 2

Model 2. Direct Effects for the “Perceived Environment → Self-regulation → MVPA Time” 2-group Mediation Model for the Towns/Rural Areas (With Fewer PA Facilities) Group ($n = 236$) and for the Large City (With More PA Facilities) Group ($n = 357$)

Note. T1 = Time 1, the baseline; T2 = Time 2, 8 months after T1; * $p < .05$, ** $p < .01$, *** $p < .001$. Red solid arrows represent significant indirect effect. Solid black arrows represent significant paths. Dashed grey arrows represent non-significant paths.